

Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats

Deliverable 4.2

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The report represents the most up to date status of the information. Any potential upcoming information may be considered for incorporation in future deliverables to improve the scientific knowledge.

The MPA Europe project

MPA Europe is a project co-funded by the European Union (EU) that will map a network of locations representative of biodiversity in European seas (Atlantic Exclusive Economic Zones of the EU and its neighbours, and all the Mediterranean, Baltic, and Black seas) (Figure A).

Figure A. MPA Europe study area.

This network will indicate where to prioritise placement of Marine Protected Areas (MPA) for biodiversity protection and how Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) can maximise blue carbon benefits. By using a holistic set of biodiversity measures, from species to ecosystems (including habitats), and environmental data including carbon storage, water currents, and climate change velocity models, it will be possible to quantify and map both the present and future connectivity within the proposed MPA network. The multiple scenarios provided will support wider and improved MSP by policy makers, industry, and non-governmental organizations (NGOs). The major scientific areas of the project and its outcomes are summarized in the infographic presented in Figure B.

Figure B. MPA Europe project scientific areas

The inter-disciplinary approach of MPA Europe is supported by a diversity of partners. These include Nord University (Norway), the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (Belgium), Aarhus University (Denmark), Climazul (Greece), the Centre of Marine Sciences (Portugal), Science Crunchers (Portugal), the Joint Nature Conservation Committee (England, UK), the Scottish Association for Marine Science (Scotland, UK), the Ocean University of China (China), and the University of the Ryukyus (Japan). The partners include experts in marine biology, taxonomy, ecology, oceanography, biogeochemistry, and biogeography, MPA network design, benthic habitat mapping, carbon dynamics, species distribution, climate modelling, and MSP compose the MPA Europe team.

Deliverable 4.2 overview

Deliverable 4.2 *Database of carbon storage in European marine non-biogenic sediment habitats* serves as a data descriptor, detailing the data acquisition processes, and procedures involved in generating spatially and standardized sediment organic carbon (OC), blue carbon, data for European seas. The data shows overall lower and less variable organic carbon content within non-biogenic habitats compared with biogenic habitats and the broader concept of “vegetated biogenic habitats” (see Deliverable 4.1 Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats).

The blue carbon database forms background information for mapping of organic carbon levels in European seas, which is relevant for the designation of Marine Protected Areas (MPAs). In subsequent tasks, the blue carbon data will be analysed in relation to habitat and environmental characteristics to identify potential drivers of carbon levels and to develop a scoring system for blue carbon in European seas. The resulting blue carbon map will feed into MPA Europe’s prioritisation tool and systematic conservation planning approach (WP5) to design MPA networks that maximize marine biodiversity and carbon stocks within the MPAs.

Background

See Deliverable 4.1 for a review of marine organic carbon (Blue Carbon), including methods for organic carbon measurements, and how the MPA Europe Euro-Carbon database was compiled (Figure 1). Data contributors are listed in Appendix 1. In addition to the biogenic habitats reported in Deliverable 4.1 (Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats), we classified samples according to their presence in EUNIS non-biogenic habitats (Appendix 2).

Figure 1. The MPA Europe Euro-Carbon database at a first glance. Overview of the data received until 31st of October 2023.

Results

A map of where samples were collected, the frequency distribution and statistics of organic carbon in the samples were provided in Deliverable 4.1 (*Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats*).

When considering the top 10 cm of sediment data divided according to the EUNIS classification of seabed, there are large variations in the % OC contents of both non-biogenic and EUNIS sediment habitats (Figure 5A). However, the % OC contents were on average higher in the biogenic habitats (average: 3.98 ± 4.07 , median: 2.46) compared with the non-biogenic (average: 1.49 ± 1.53 , median: 1.05) sediments.

In this first overview of data, we have simply compared OC-content of the unvegetated non-biogenic habitats (Figure 5B, below) with that of the vegetated biogenic habitats (see Deliverable 4.1, Figure 5B).

The unvegetated subtidal areas (1.96 ± 1.98) had marginally higher OC content in the top 10 cm of the sediment followed by unvegetated intertidal (1.44 ± 1.23) and deep sea (1.14 ± 0.70) habitats (Table 4, Figure 5B). Interestingly the OC values in the non-biogenic habitats had lower coefficient

of variation (CV i.e. dispersion of the data around the mean) than the biogenic habitats (broader definition) suggesting that non-biogenic habitats are more uniform in their %OC content (Table 4). See Deliverable 4.1 (*Database of estimated carbon storage in European marine biogenic habitats*) for further information on biogenic habitats.

In subsequent analyses, we will quantify and compare OC levels for the various categories of non-biogenic sediment types under EUNIS classification of seabed habitats (i.e. fine mud, sand, coarse substratum mixed sediment, muddy sand, rock or other hard substrata, sediment, sandy mud or muddy sand, fine mud or sandy mud or muddy sand) and also analyse OC levels as functions of other environmental drivers.

Figure 5. Box plots of the averaged organic carbon (OC %) content in the top 10 cm of the sediment for (A) habitats divided according to EUNIS into non-biogenic and biogenic habitats (in this case *Posidonia oceanica* (MB252), Atlantic infralittoral *Serpula vermicularis* reefs (MB2212), *Limaria hians* beds in tide-swept Atlantic infralittoral muddy mixed sediment (MB2221) and bivalve reefs in the Atlantic infralittoral zone (MB222)) and (B) non-biogenic, unvegetated sediment subdivided based on sample water depth: unvegetated intertidal (-1m to -3.3m), unvegetated subtidal (0 to -250 m), Deep sea (>-250 m). The lines represent median values, the limits of the boxes represent 25-75 percentiles, and the whiskers extend from the limit of the box to the largest and smallest values but no further than 1.5*IQR (inter quartile range). NA = sediment information not available. See Deliverable 4.1 for further details on biogenic habitats.

Table 4. Summary statistics for the average organic carbon (OC %) content in the top 10 cm of the sediment for (A) non-biogenic and biogenic habitats according to EUNIS definition and (B) non-biogenic unvegetated sediment subdivided based on sample water depth: unvegetated intertidal (-1m to 3.3m), unvegetated subtidal (0 to -250 m), deep sea (> 250 m). The minimum, maximum, average values (\pm standard deviation, SD), median, coefficient of variance (CV), 25th and 75th percentiles (%tiles) and number of samples (N) are shown. NA=sediment information not available.

Organic carbon								
	Minimum	Maximum	Average \pm SD	Median	CV	25 % tiles	75 % tiles	N
A								
Non-biogenic	0	20.3	1.49 \pm 1.53	1.05	102.7	0.48	2.02	4040
Biogenic	0.14	21.0	3.98 \pm 4.07	2.46	102.3	1.14	5.12	153
NA	0.02	22.1	2.18 \pm 2.47	1.02	113.3	0.64	2.70	2604
B								
Unvegetated intertidal	0.03	5.8	1.44 \pm 1.23	1.25	85.4	0.32	2.15	105
Unvegetated subtidal	0	22.1	1.96 \pm 1.98	1.46	101.0	0.60	2.47	3456
Deep sea	0.04	6.7	1.14 \pm 0.70	0.95	61.4	0.60	1.56	1165

Next steps

Within the next months we will

- Finalize the compilation of additional data from available database and the peer-reviewed literature.
- Complete quality control of the final dataset to ensure it is consistent.
- Publish the database, coauthored by all data providers, through a publicly available data publisher (e.g. Pangaea).
- Write and publish, along with the database, a data manuscript describing the dataset, coauthored by all data providers.

Acknowledgements

All data contributors are listed in Appendix 1.

Appendix

Appendix 1. Name and institution of the data Contributors until 31st of October 2023

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Appendix 2. List of EUNIS 2019 non-biogenic habitats available in the dataset.

EUNIS 2019 non-biogenic habitats

Deep circalittoral

MB12: Atlantic infralittoral rock

MB13: Baltic infralittoral rock

MB15: Mediterranean infralittoral rock

MB32: Atlantic infralittoral coarse sediment

MB33: Baltic infralittoral coarse sediment

MB34: Black Sea infralittoral coarse sediment

MB35: Mediterranean infralittoral coarse sediment

MB42: Atlantic infralittoral mixed sediment

MB43: Baltic infralittoral mixed sediment

MB52: Atlantic infralittoral sand

MB53 or MB63: Baltic infralittoral sand or Baltic infralittoral mud

MB53: Baltic infralittoral sand

MB54: Black Sea infralittoral sand

MB55: Mediterranean infralittoral sand

MB62: Atlantic infralittoral mud

MB63: Baltic infralittoral mud

MB65: Mediterranean infralittoral mud

MB652: Assemblages of the euryhaline and/or eurythermal lagoon biocenosis on mud

MC12: Atlantic circalittoral rock

MC13: Baltic circalittoral rock

MC32: Atlantic circalittoral coarse sediment

MC33: Baltic circalittoral coarse sediment

MC35: Mediterranean circalittoral coarse sediment

MC42: Atlantic circalittoral mixed sediment

MC43: Baltic circalittoral mixed sediment

MC44: Black Sea circalittoral mixed sediment

MC45: Mediterranean circalittoral mixed sediment

MC451: Biocenosis of Mediterranean muddy detritic bottoms

MC52: Atlantic circalittoral sand

MC53 or MC63: Baltic circalittoral sand or Baltic circalittoral mud

MC53: Baltic circalittoral sand

MC55: Mediterranean Circalittoral sand

MC62: Atlantic circalittoral mud

MC63: Baltic circalittoral mud

MC64: Black Sea circalittoral mud

MC651: Biocenosis of Mediterranean circalittoral coastal terrigenous muds

MD12: Atlantic offshore circalittoral rock

MD32: Atlantic offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

MD33: Baltic offshore circalittoral coarse sediment

MD42: Atlantic offshore circalittoral mixed sediment

EUNIS 2019 non-biogenic habitats

MD43: Baltic offshore circalittoral mixed sediment
MD44: Black Sea offshore circalittoral mixed sediment
MD451: Biocenosis of Mediterranean open-sea detritic bottoms on shelf-edge
MD52: Atlantic offshore circalittoral sand
MD53 or MD63: Baltic offshore circalittoral sand or Baltic offshore circalittoral mud
MD53: Baltic offshore circalittoral sand
MD62: Atlantic offshore circalittoral mud
MD63: Baltic offshore circalittoral mud
MD64: Black Sea offshore circalittoral mud
MD651: Biocenosis of Mediterranean offshore circalittoral coastal terrigenous muds
ME11: Arctic upper bathyal rock
ME12: Atlantic upper bathyal rock
ME31: Arctic upper bathyal coarse sediment
ME32: Atlantic upper bathyal coarse sediment
ME41: Arctic upper bathyal mixed sediment
ME42: Atlantic upper bathyal mixed sediment
ME51: Arctic upper bathyal sand
ME52: Atlantic upper bathyal sand
ME61: Arctic upper bathyal mud
ME62: Atlantic upper bathyal mud
ME64 or MF64: Black Sea upper bathyal mud or Black Sea lower bathyal mud
ME65: Mediterranean upper bathyal mud
MF52: Atlantic lower bathyal sand
MF61: Arctic lower bathyal mud
MF62: Atlantic lower bathyal mud
MF65 or MF55: Mediterranean lower bathyal mud or Mediterranean lower bathyal sand
MF65: Mediterranean lower bathyal mud
MG12: Atlantic abyssal rock
MG52: Atlantic abyssal sand
MG61: Arctic abyssal mud
MG62: Atlantic abyssal mud
MG64: Black Sea abyssal mud
MG65: Mediterranean abyssal mud
Shallow circalittoral
